

Cosolvency Studies of Polyethylene. Part—II : Viscometric Studies in Different Cosolvent Media

NITA VIDYARTHI* (nee DAS) and SANTI R. PALIT

Department of Physical Chemistry, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Jadavpur, Calcutta-700 032

Manuscript received 14 May 1980, revised 14 July 1981, accepted 26 February 1982

Polyethylene (PE), though insoluble in all solvents near room temperature, has been found to be soluble in a number of binary mixtures, one of which is CS_2 . η_{sp}/c vs c plots for such systems have been found to be consistently of negative slope and in a few cases, this negative slope at low dilution is so pronounced as to appear like the 'upswing', typical of polyelectrolytes. The Mark-Houwink constants in a few such cosolvent pairs have been determined at a number of temperatures. Besides, the intrinsic viscosity-molecular weight relationship deduced theoretically by Palit has also been tested and found to be satisfactory. Further, the viscometric data have been utilised to calculate the unperturbed dimensions of PE (at different temperatures) by the use of Stockmayer-Fixman equation which agrees well with literature data. However, the viscosity data do not comply with the expectation of the theories of Kurata-Stockmayer-Roig or Flory-Schaeffgen or Ptitsyn which may be due to a difference in composition of the solution layer and the bulk of the solution.

VISCOSITY studies of polyethylene (PE) in single solvents are rare and those in cosolvent media do not seem to exist. Some data on the constants of Mark-Houwink equation and molecular dimensions at high temperature in single solvents have been reported^{1,2}. This communication reports a study of low density PE in a mixture of cosolvents. The cosolvents being a mixture of two nonsolvents with latent dissolving power such that the polymer dissolves in their mixture of suitable composition^{3,4}.

Experimental

Materials : The low density polyethylenes used in the present studies were the same as those obtained from I.C.I. (India) Ltd. and Union Carbide (U.S.A.) and used in an earlier study⁴.

All solvents, excepting THF and CS_2 , were of A. R. grade and were distilled before use. THF and CS_2 were subjected to further purification by standard methods^{3,4}.

Determination of molecular weight : Molecular weights of the different polymer fractions were determined by measuring the osmotic pressure of their xylene solutions at 60° in a Hewlett-Packard 501 high speed membrane osmometer. The molecular weights were calculated according to van't Hoff's equation,

$$\left(\frac{\pi}{c}\right)_{c \rightarrow 0} = \frac{RT}{M_n} \quad \dots (1)$$

where symbols are of usual significance. However, for the unfractionated polymer, the molecular weights supplied by the manufactures were used.

Measurement of intrinsic viscosity : Solution viscosity measurements were made at several concentrations with various cosolvent compositions and at different temperatures in an Ubbelohde dilution viscometer for which kinetic energy corrections are negligible. Intrinsic viscosities were obtained by extrapolation of the η_{sp}/c vs c plots to zero concentration (c , the concentration of the polymer solution being expressed in g/dl) in accordance with the Huggins' equation⁶

$$\eta_{sp}/c = [\eta] + k' [\eta]^2 c \quad \dots (2)$$

where k' is a constant (Huggins' constant) for a series of polymers of different molecular weights in a given solvent.

Results and Discussion

Intrinsic viscosity and Huggins' constant k' : Viscosity results for fractionated and unfractionated samples soluble at 30° are presented in Tables 1 and 2. The η_{sp}/c vs c plots are linear but have a negative slope (vide Fig. 1 for representative plots) and so k' is negative. Normally, k' lies between 0.35 to 0.40. Hence our values cannot be interpreted in the light of Huggins theory.

Anomalous viscosity behaviour : Some of our η_{sp}/c vs c plots in solvents like a mixture of 50 : 50 cyclohexane- CS_2 show an unexpected behaviour of having an upswing as c approaches 0 (<0.1 g/dl). Such observations for polyvinyl chloride⁶⁻¹⁴ have been attributed by Ohn¹⁵ to the adsorption of polymer on the walls of the capillary. This, however, cannot be true in our case as the viscosity measurements were made not only through dilutions inside the viscometer but were repeated by using

* Present address : Department of Chemistry, St. Xavier's College, 30 Park Street, Calcutta-16,

TABLE 1—VALUES OF $[\eta]$ (k' HUGGINS' CONSTANT) FOR DIFFERENT UNFRACTIONATED POLYMERS IN VARIOUS COSOLVENT MEDIA AT 30°

Sample		E	D	F	WSG-22	G	H
$\bar{M}_n \times 10^{-3}$		33	31	25	21	12	4
$[\eta]$ dl/g	in			Xylene - CS ₂			
	75 : 25	1.15(-0.59)	1.07(-0.87)	0.90(-0.94)	0.86(-1.83)	—	0.19(-7.47)
	80 : 20	—	0.65(-1.66)	0.58(-1.90)	—	0.34(-1.99)	0.23(-15.83)
$[\eta]$ dl/g	in			CHCl ₃ - CS ₂			
	50 : 50	0.59(-1.19)	0.56(-2.34)	0.53(-2.52)	0.49(-2.78)	0.40(-5.68)	0.29(-8.60)
	55 : 45	0.63(-1.09)	0.59(-1.71)	0.58(-1.81)	0.54(-2.31)	0.44(-4.03)	0.32(-5.05)
	60 : 40	0.68(-1.61)	0.52(-2.47)	0.52(-2.47)	0.49(-2.83)	0.39(-4.55)	0.28(-8.43)
$[\eta]$ dl/g	in			CCl ₄ - CS ₂			
	55 : 45	0.74(-1.37)	0.59(-0.80)	0.60(-0.68)	—	0.37(-5.01)	0.16(-25.46)
	60 : 40	0.69(-1.1)	0.60(-3.12)	0.49(-0.70)	0.46(-4.65)	0.33(-6.49)	0.16(-24.46)
$[\eta]$ dl/g	in			Cyclohexane - CS ₂			
	45 : 55	—	—	0.86(-0.86)	—	0.54(-2.31)	0.27(-10.88)
	50 : 50	0.89	0.83*	0.78*	1.56*	—	—
$[\eta]$ dl/g	in			THF - CS ₂			
	45 : 55	—	0.60(-1.41)	0.40(-3.56)	0.39(-5.03)	0.36(-0.63)	—
	50 : 50	—	0.62(-1.25)	0.39(-5.58)	0.40(-3.84)	0.32(-6.17)	0.23(-14.24)
	55 : 45	—	0.68(-1.04)	0.41(-3.35)	0.38(-4.79)	0.22(-8.26)	0.19(-16.79)

* Exhibits anomalous viscosity, $[\eta]$ values determined from Fuoss' equation (3). The bracketted values are the corresponding k' values.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF $[\eta]$ (AND HUGGINS' CONSTANT k') FOR DIFFERENT FRACTIONATED POLYMERS IN VARIOUS COSOLVENT MEDIA AT 30°

Fraction		1	2	3	4	5	6
$\bar{M}_n \times 10^{-3}$		196.0	47.10	46.40	25.10	20.38	19.14
$[\eta]$ dl/g	in			Xylene - CS ₂			
	75 : 25	—	0.51(-4.61)	0.41(-5.36)	0.21(-11.62)	0.16(-16.00)	0.15(-29.29)
	80 : 20	—	1.08(-0.68)	1.05(-0.91)	0.39(-4.61)	0.19(-22.22)	0.16(-18.21)
$[\eta]$ dl/g	in			CHCl ₃ - CS ₂			
	50 : 50	12.01(-0.16)	—	—	—	0.91(-9.13)	0.27(-9.86)
	55 : 45	—	—	1.26(-0.37)	—	0.95(-5.21)	0.32(-5.60)
$[\eta]$ dl/g	in			CCl ₄ - CS ₂			
	55 : 45	—	0.56(-2.27)	0.54(-2.30)	0.46(-2.56)	0.38(-5.34)	0.34(-6.13)
	60 : 40	—	0.62(-2.19)	0.60(-2.50)	0.50(-2.65)	—	—
$[\eta]$ dl/g	in			Cyclohexane - CS ₂			
	45 : 55	—	0.66(-0.40)	0.64(-0.78)	0.52(-1.18)	—	0.24(-2.19)
	*50 : 50	—	0.86	0.55	0.83	—	0.60
$[\eta]$ dl/g	in			THF - CS ₂			
	45 : 55	—	—	1.12(-0.57)	—	—	0.34(-0.69)
	50 : 50	—	0.57(-0.73)	—	0.50(-2.39)	0.48(-2.59)	—
	55 : 45	—	0.83(-0.50)	—	—	0.41(-2.39)	—

* Exhibits anomalous viscosity, $[\eta]$ values determined from Fuoss' equation (3). The bracketted values are the corresponding k' values.

in each case fresh solutions of different concentrations prepared outside and the same results were obtained.

Polyelectrolytes are well known to exhibit such upswing due to intramolecular coulombic repulsion^{1,6} which evidently does not apply in our case. Ours is probably the result of pronounced negative slope of η_{sp}/c vs c curves. Our data can be formally treated by the equation proposed by Fuoss^{1,7} for polyelectrolytes, i.e.,

$$\eta_{sp}/c = \frac{A}{1 + Bc^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad \dots (3)$$

(where A and B are constants) to obtain the value of $[\eta]$ which cannot be obtained by normal extrapolation method. Plots of $(\eta_{sp}/c)^{-1}$ against $c^{1/2}$ give straight lines in all cases. The above anomaly (upswing), however, disappears with rise of temperature and shows the usual linearity with negative slopes. This sensitivity to high temperature may be due to structure formation at low temperature.

Intrinsic viscosity-molecular weight relationship :

(i) *Mark-Houwink equation :* The Mark-Houwink constants have been evaluated by plotting $\log [\eta]$ values reported in Tables 1 and 2 against $\log \bar{M}_n$ in

Fig. 1. Plot of $[\eta]$ vs concentration of fractionated samples in 75 : 25 xylene- CS_2 mixture at 30°.

accordance with Mark-Houwink equation¹⁸ $[\eta] = K'M^a$. Fairly good linear plots are obtained in all cases. The Mark-Houwink constants are reported in Table 3.

The K' values are normal for most polymers and are of the order of 10^{-4} . The 'a' value though theoretically expected to lie between 0.5 to 1, show an extensive range of values varying from as low a value of 0.2 to 0.9. Since $\ominus$ solvents have a value of 0.5, it appears that in such cosolvent media, the concept of $\ominus$ solvents does not apply unambiguously.

For the fractionated polymer in xylene- CS_2 (80 : 20), THF- CS_2 (45 : 55) and (55 : 45) and the unfractionated polymer in xylene- CS_2 (80 : 20), the 'a' values are close to 0.5 at 30° and so they may be considered to be under $\ominus$ condition. From consideration of the 'a' values and its temperature sensitivity, and low minimum T_g and less volatility and toxicity, we recommend xylene- CS_2 (75 : 25) and (80 : 20) at around 35° for routine use for viscometric molecular weight determination of PE by Mark-Houwink method.

(ii) *Effect of temperature*: We have determined the effect of change of temperature on $[\eta]$

TABLE 3—MARK HOUWINK'S CONSTANT FOR FRACTIONATED AND UNFRACTIONATED PE IN DIFFERENT COSOLVENT MEDIA AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES

Cosolvent system	Cosolvent composition v/v	Sample	Temp. °C	$k' \times 10^4$	a	
Xylene- CS_2	75 : 25	fractionated	30	2793	0.27	
	75 : 25	unfractionated	30	17.49	0.83	
	80 : 20	unfractionated	30	102	0.57	
	80 : 20	fractionated	30	412	0.45	
" "	" "	" "	34	3.29	0.88	
	" "	" "	37	4.0	0.87	
	CHCl_3 - CS_2	50 : 50	unfractionated	30	1858	0.33
		50 : 50	fractionated	30	4.13	0.90
50 : 50		fractionated	34	1629	0.34	
50 : 50		fractionated	37	1747	0.37	
" "	55 : 45	unfractionated	30	1842	0.34	
	60 : 40	fractionated	30	60.5	0.64	
	60 : 40	unfractionated	30	1271	0.36	
	CCl_4 - CS_2	55 : 45	unfractionated	30	27.91	0.74
60 : 40		fractionated	30	13700	0.12	
60 : 40		unfractionated	30	80.46	0.64	
60 : 40		fractionated	30	26220	0.08	
" "	" "	" "	34	28990	0.10	
	" "	" "	37	17910	0.15	
	Cyclohexane- CS_2	45 : 55	fractionated	30	2755	0.29
		50 : 50	" "	30	1182	0.42
" "		" "	34	10600	0.20	
" "		" "	37	4499	0.28	
THF- CS_2	45 : 55	unfractionated	30	3141	0.26	
	" "	fractionated	30	207	0.52	
	50 : 50	unfractionated	30	1656	0.32	
	" "	fractionated	30	25410	0.07	
	55 : 45	unfractionated	30	473	0.44	
	" "	fractionated	30	249	0.54	
" "	" "	34	1933	0.30		
" "	" "	37	2823	0.22		

and the Mark-Houwink constants. Results are recorded in Tables 3 and 4, respectively. The constant 'a' is often found to be very sensitive to change of temperature. Sometimes, the value increases enormously with slight change of temperature, e.g., in xylene- CS_2 , 'a' changes from 0.45 at 30° to 0.88 and 0.87 at 34° and 37°, respectively. This, however, is exceptional and in other systems, 'a' is generally found to decrease somewhat with temperature. Evidently, solvent power as judged by the values of 'a' has no simple relationship with temperature in such cosolvent systems.

Since the temperature dependence on $[\eta]$ according to Fox-Flory¹⁹ treatment depends on the nature of the solvent and since our systems are rather close to $\ominus$ temperature (i.e., poor solvents) it is expected that $[\eta]$ should increase with increase in temperature. We have observed this in most cases and evidently the explanation seems to be that the expansion factor α increases with the increase in temperature.

A remarkably different case is the system THF- CS_2 where $[\eta]$ values decrease sharply over a small temperature interval, e.g., for fraction 2, the $[\eta]$ values are 0.83 at 30°, 0.67 at 34° and 0.403 at 37°, respectively. Such variations are very unusual and

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON THE INTRINSIC VISCOSITY (AND HUGGINS' CONSTANT k') OF FRACTIONATED PE IN DIFFERENT COSOLVENT MEDIA AT THEIR OPTIMUM SOLVENT COMPOSITIONS

Fraction		1	2	3	4	5	6
		Xylene- CS_2 80 : 20					
[η] dl/g							
at	30°	—	1.08(-0.68)	1.05(-0.64)	0.99(-4.61)	0.19(-22.22)	0.16(-18.21)
	34°	—	1.07(-1.71)	—	0.25(-4.61)	0.15(-28.68)	—
	37°	—	0.94(-0.24)	—	0.27(-6.81)	0.11(-34.45)	—
		$CHCl_3$ - CS_2 50 : 50					
[η] dl/g							
at	30°	12.01(-0.16)	—	—	—	0.81(-9.13)	0.27(-9.86)
	34°	—	0.63(-2.65)	0.62(-3.10)	—	0.33(-2.15)	—
	37°	—	0.93(-1.06)	0.91(-1.20)	—	0.45(-3.02)	—
		CCl_4 - CS_2 60 : 40					
[η] dl/g							
at	30°	—	0.62(-2.19)	0.60(-2.50)	0.50(-2.65)	—	—
	34°	—	0.87(-1.05)	—	0.64(-3.50)	0.58(-2.54)	—
	37°	—	1.11(-0.39)	—	0.71(-1.01)	0.60(-1.64)	—
		Cyclohexane- CS_2 50 : 50					
[η] dl/g							
at	*30°	—	*0.86	*0.55	*0.83	—	*0.60
	34°	—	0.91(-0.46)	—	0.67(-0.68)	—	0.61(-1.27)
	37°	—	1.19(-0.16)	—	0.77(-0.67)	—	0.64(-1.22)
		THF- CS_2 55 : 45					
[η] dl/g							
at	30°	—	0.83(-0.50)	—	—	0.41(-2.39)	—
	34°	—	0.67(-1.97)	—	—	0.39(-3.50)	—
	37°	—	0.403(-1.15)	—	—	0.254(-5.20)	0.247(-7.11)

* Exhibits anomalous viscosity, [η] determined from Fuoss' equation (3)

All bracketted values are k' values.

Fig. 2. Palit plots for the fractionated samples in different cosolvents at different temperatures

Cyclohexane- CS_2	Temp
(a) 45 : 55	30°
(b) 50 : 50	34°
(c) 50 : 50	37°
$CHCl_3$ - CS_2	
(d) 55 : 45	30°
(e) 50 : 50	30°
(f) 50 : 50	34°
(g) 50 : 50	37°

should probably be attributed to the critical nature of differential solvation by the cosolvents.

(iii) The Palit relationship: A correlation between the intrinsic viscosity and molecular weight of polymers has been deduced by Palit²⁰. The equation is given as

$$100\rho_0[\eta] + \ln M = K_1 M^{2/3} + K_2 \quad (4)$$

where ρ_0 is the partial specific density of the polymer at infinite dilution. A plot of $100\rho_0[\eta] + \ln M$ vs $M^{2/3}$ should be linear and our data fit quite well and the linearity is pretty good in all the cases of both fractionated and unfractionated polymers studied in all the five cosolvent systems at 30, 34 and 37° as is evident from Figs. 2 and 3. So, this relationship is not only applicable to simple solvents²¹⁻²³ but also to PE in cosolvents.

Determination of the unperturbed dimensions of PE in cosolvent media through the use of Stockmayer-Fixman equation: Since we were unsuccessful in determining Θ temperature by conventional methods, we took recourse to the following equation of Stockmayer and Fixman²⁴ to estimate the unperturbed dimension viz.,

$$[\eta]/M^{1/2} = K + 0.51 \phi BM^{1/2} \quad \dots (5)$$

$$K = \phi \langle r^2 \rangle_0 \phi M^{3/2}$$

The values of K obtained from the Stockmayer-Fixman plots are reported in Table 5. Exceptionally low values of K obtained for a few other systems are not reported herein.

For the unfractionated polymer, the value of $\langle r^2 \rangle_0/M^{1/2}$ for 55 : 45 CCl_4 - CS_2 agrees excellently with those of Kurata and Stockmayer²⁵. The interesting point is that they had carried

Fig. 3. Palit plots for the unfractionated samples in different cosolvents at 30°.

Xylene- CS_2 (a) 75 : 25 (b) 80 : 20
 Cyclohexane- CS_2 (c) 45 : 55 (d) 50 : 50
 CCl_4 - CS_2 (e) 60 : 40 (f) 55 : 45

TABLE 5—UNPERTURBED CHAIN DIMENSIONS FOR PE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND IN DIFFERENT COSOLVENT MEDIA, CALCULATED FROM K VALUES (LITERATURE VALUE 950 ± 40)²³

Cosolvent system	Cosolvent composition	Sample	$K \times 10^5$	Temp. °C	$(\langle r^2 \rangle / M)^{1/2} \times 10^{11}$
Xylene- CS_2	75 : 25	unfractionated	130	30	767.94
	80 : 20	"	360	30	1077.50
Cyclohexane- CS_2	45 : 55	unfractionated	340	30	1057.90
	"	fractionated	415	30	1131.00
	50 : 50	unfractionated	480	30	1186.90
	"	fractionated	470	34	1178.40
CCl_4 - CS_2	"	"	300	37	1014.80
	55 : 45	unfractionated	230	30	928.82
	"	fractionated	198	30	883.57
	60 : 40	unfractionated	180	30	855.95
THF- CS_2	"	fractionated	400	34	1114.60
	"	"	268	37	977.39
	45 : 55	unfractionated	500	30	1203.10
	50 : 50	"	420	30	1135.30
	"	fractionated	480	30	1186.90
	55 : 45	unfractionated	325	30	1042.00
$CHCl_3$ - CS_2	"	fractionated	92	30	648.35
	"	"	160	34	822.98
	"	"	180	37	855.95
	50 : 50	unfractionated	420	30	1135.30
	"	fractionated	82	34	658.62
	55 : 45	unfractionated	92	37	658.62
	60 : 40	unfractionated	495	30	1199.20
	"	"	520	30	1220.40

are independent of temperature and solvent type. As is evident from Table 5 the values in general are slightly higher than those of the fractionated polymers but there is a fair degree of consistency among the results.

Fig. 4. Stockmayer Fixman plots for (i) fractionated samples in cyclohexane- CS_2 at different temperatures

Cyclohexane- CS_2 Temp.
 (a) 45 : 55 30°
 (b) 50 : 50 34°
 (c) 50 : 50 37°

out experiments at 100° and the present investigations were all carried out in the vicinity of room temperature. This is in accordance with the general concept that the unperturbed dimensions

(ii) unfractionated samples in different cosolvents at 30°.

Xylene-CS ₂	(1) 75 : 25	(2) 80 : 20
Cyclohexane-CS ₂	(3) 45 : 55	
CCl ₄ -CS ₂	(4) 60 : 40	(5) 55 : 45
THF-CS ₂	(6) 55 : 45	

References

1. "Polymer Handbook", (Ed.) J. BRANDRUP and E. M. IMMERGUT, Interscience Publishers, New York, 1966, p. 8.
2. H. L. WAGNER and C. A. J. HREVE, *J. Poly. Sci. Polym. Sym.*, 1976, 54, 53.
3. N. DAS and S. R. PALIT, *J. Poly. Sci. Polymer Chem. Educ.*, 1973, 11, 1025.
4. N. VIDYARTHI (nee DAS) and S. R. PALIT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, 59, 748.
5. M. L. HUGGINS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 2716.
6. T. KAWAI and K. SAITO, *J. Poly. Sci.*, 1957, 26, 213.
7. B. J. STREETER and R. F. BOYER, *J. Poly. Sci.*, 1954, 14, 5.
8. H. BATZER, *Die Makromol. Chem.*, 1954, 12, 145.
9. H. UMSTATTER, *Die Makromol. Chem.*, 1954, 12, 94.
10. H. KOBAYASHI, *Chem. High Polym., Japan*, 1955, 12, 266.
11. I. K. EDELMAN, *Faserforsch. U. Textil Tech.*, 1954, 5, 325.
12. I. K. EDELMAN, *Faserforsch. U. Textil Tech.*, 1954, 5, 189.
13. I. K. EDELMAN, *Faserforsch. U. Textil Tech.*, 1955, 6, 269.
14. F. PATAT and H. G. ELIAS, *Die Makromol. Chem.*, 1954, 16, 40.
15. O. E. OHRN, *J. Poly. Sci.*, 1955, 17, 187.
16. P. J. FLORY, "Principles of Polymer Chemistry", Cornell Univ. Press, 1953, Ithaca, N. Y., p. 636.
17. R. M. FUOSS and U. P. STRAUSS, *Annals N. Y. Acad. Sci.*, 1949, 51, 836.
18. "Polymer Handbook", (Ed.), J. BRANDRUP and E. M. IMMERGUT, Interscience Publishers, New York, 1966, p. 2.
19. P. J. FLORY, "Principles of Polymer Chemistry", Cornell Univ. Press, Ithaca, N. Y., 1953, Chap. 14.
20. S. R. PALIT, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1955, 29, 65.
21. D. K. SARKAR and S. R. PALIT, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1967, 41, 389.
22. D. K. SARKAR and S. R. PALIT, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1969, 43, 23.
23. S. H. WU and K. G. MAYHAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 1082.
24. W. STOCKMAYER and M. FIXMAN, *J. Poly. Sci.*, 1963, C1, 137.
25. M. KURATA and W. STOCKMAYER, *Hochpolym-Forsch.*, 1963, 3, 196.